

Descriptor Tables in the STING Database

Air	Catalytic_Residue	Side_Chain_Orientation_GN	Solvation_WNA
Electrostatic_Potential	chain_arranged	Cross_Presence_Order_SW	Space_Clash
Electrostatic_Potential_GN	Mouth_Atom	Side_Chain_Orientation_SW	Density_Sponge
Electrostatic_Potential_SW	Chain	Cross_Presence_Order_VD	Density_Sponge_DNA
Electrostatic_Potential_VD	Mouth	Side_Chain_Orientation_VD	Sting_HSSP
Electrostatic_Potential_WNA	Multiple_Sequence_Alignment	Cross_Presence_Order_WNA	Density_Sponge_DNA_GN
Energy_Density	Contact	Side_Chain_Orientation_WNA	Stride
Energy_Density_GN	Pocket_Atom	Curvature_Atom	Density_Sponge_DNA_SW
Energy_Density_VD	Prosite	Curvature	Structure
Energy_Density_WNA	Cross_Link_Order	Solvation	Density_Sponge_DNA_VD
Entropy_Density	Protein_Ligand_Contact	Curvature_GN	Density_Sponge_DNA_WNA
Entropy_Density_GN	Cross_Link_Order_GN	Solvation_GN	Unused_Contacts
Entropy_Density_SW	Cross_Link_Order_SW	Curvature_SW	Density_Sponge_GN
Entropy_Density_WNA	Residue_Contacts	Solvation_SW	Unused_Contacts_GN
EPAAtom	Cross_Link_Order_VD	Curvature_VD	Density_Sponge_SW
Evolutionary_Pressure	Residue_Contacts_GN	Solvation_VD	Unused_Contacts_SW
Atom_ASA	Cross_Link_Order_WNA	Curvature_WNA	Density_Sponge_VD
FPocket_Atom	Residue_Contacts_WNA	Solvation_WNA	Unused_Contacts_VD
atom_asa_dataframe	Cross_Presence_Order	Curvature_Atom	Density_Sponge_WNA
FPocket	Cross_Presence_Order_DNA_GN	Curvature	Unused_Contacts_WNA
Atom	Rotamer	Solvation	Weighted_Contact_Number
Graph_Descriptor	Cross_Presence_Order_DNA_SW	Curvature_GN	Distances
Graph_Descriptor_SW	scaled_balanced_sponged	Solvation_GN	Weighted_Contact_Number_GN
Graph_Descriptor_VD	Cross_Presence_Order_DNA_VD	Curvature_SW	distribution.png
Graph_Descriptor_WNA	Cross_Presence_Order_DNA_WNA	Solvation_SW	Weighted_Contact_Number_SW
HSSP	Side_Chain_Orientation	Curvature_VD	DSSP
Ligand_Pocket_And_Water_Contact	Cross_Presence_Order_GN	Solvation_VD	Weighted_Contact_Number_VD
		Curvature_WNA	EFR_slides
			Weighted_Contact_Number_WNA

All tables from the STING database were selectively retrieved to match the PDB_ID codes from the Allosteric database.

Descriptor Tables in the STING Database

Air

Electrostatic_Potential

Electrostatic_Potential_GN

Electrostatic_Potential_SW

Electrostatic_Potential_VD

Electrostatic_Potential_WNA

Energy_Density

Energy_Density_GN

Energy_Density_VD

Energy_Density_WNA

Entropy_Density

Entropy_Density_GN

Entropy_Density_SW

Entropy_Density_WNA

FPocket

Graph_Descriptor

Graph_Descriptor_SW

Graph_Descriptor_SW

Graph_Descriptor_VD

Graph_Descriptor_WNA

HSSP

Cross_Link_Order_GN

Cross_Link_Order_SW

Cross_Link_Order_VD

Residue_Contacts_GN

Cross_Link_Order_WNA

Residue_Contacts_WNA

Side_Chain_Orientation

Cross_Presence_Order_GN

Side_Chain_Orientation_GN

Cross_Presence_Order_SW

Side_Chain_Orientation_SW

Side_Chain_Orientation_VD

Cross_Presence_Order_WNA

Side_Chain_Orientation_WNA

Curvature

Solvation

Curvature_GN

Solvation_GN

Solvation_SW

Curvature_SW

Solvation_VD

Curvature_VD

Solvation_WNA

Curvature_WNA

Space_Clash

Density_ Sponge

Density_

Sponge

Density_ Sponge

Correlation Matrix

Density_Sponge

Sting_HSSP

Stride

Density_Sponge_SW

Density_Sponge_SW

Density_Sponge_SW

Density_Sponge_GN

Density_Sponge_GN

Correlation Matrix

Density_Sponge_GN

Weighted_Contact_Number

Distances

Weighted_Contact _Number_WNA

Hypothesis Verification

In statistical terms, our null hypothesis (H_0) is that the descriptor value distributions are the same for both classes, while our alternative hypothesis (H_1) is that the descriptor value distributions are not the same.

To test this hypothesis, we applied three statistical tests. The first test was the **Kolmogorov-Smirnov test (KS)**, which is a non-parametric test used to compare the empirical distribution function of a sample to a reference probability distribution or to compare the empirical distribution functions of two samples. The KS statistic measures the maximum distance between the two empirical distribution functions.

The second test was the **Q-Q plot**, which is a graphical method for comparing two probability distributions by plotting their quantiles against each other. If the data have a normal distribution, then **Student's t-test** may be used.

Hypothesis Verification

1. Kolmogorov-Smirnov test (KS)

	Column	KS Statistic	p-value
0	density_CA_3	0.128242	1.110768e-136
1	density_CA_5	0.210097	0.000000e+00
2	density_CA_7	0.407871	0.000000e+00
3	density_LHA_4	0.212609	0.000000e+00
4	density_LHA_6	0.176447	3.308767e-259
5	density_CA_3_IFR	0.165315	2.171071e-227
6	density_CA_5_IFR	0.159295	4.550779e-211
7	density_CA_7_IFR	0.296390	0.000000e+00
8	density_LHA_4_IFR	0.179629	1.076353e-268
9	density_LHA_6_IFR	0.167219	1.111917e-232
10	sponge_CA_3	0.162763	2.146883e-220
11	sponge_CA_5	0.165524	5.737079e-228
12	sponge_CA_7	0.285503	0.000000e+00

The *p-value* is below this threshold of 0.05 for all descriptors used in the study, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected in favor of the alternative hypothesis (that the two groups (AFRs and FRs) come from different distributions)

1. Kolmogorov-Smirnov test (KS)

	Column	KS Statistic	p-value
13	sponge_LHA_4	0.137226	1.609762e-156
14	sponge_LHA_6	0.167940	1.059997e-234
15	sponge_CA_3_IFR	0.162763	2.146883e-220
16	sponge_CA_5_IFR	0.165648	2.598911e-228
17	sponge_CA_7_IFR	0.287837	0.000000e+00
18	sponge_LHA_4_IFR	0.137229	1.579567e-156
19	sponge_LHA_6_IFR	0.155896	3.964276e-202
20	hb_mm_energy_GN	0.157118	2.543096e-205
21	side_chain_average_angle_7	0.195795	1.362238e-319
22	neighbors_side_chain_angle_7	0.188539	3.479626e-296
23	background_rel_entropy	0.266057	0.000000e+00
24	avg_weighted_contact_number_k_2	0.294597	0.000000e+00

Hypothesis Verification

2. Q-Q Plot

Q-Q Plot for Non-Exosites (density_CA_3)

Q-Q Plot for Exosites (density_CA_3)

In this study, we used Q-Q plots to assess the normality of the distribution of several variables in our dataset. We split the data into two groups based on the target column and generated Q-Q plots for each group and each variable. The results showed that for most variables, the ordered values of the sample data closely followed the theoretical quantiles of the normal distribution, as indicated by the alignment of the blue points with the red line on the Q-Q plots. This suggests that the distribution of these variables is approximately normal in both groups. These findings have important implications for our analysis, as many statistical methods assume that the data follows a normal distribution.

Hypothesis Verification

2. Q-Q Plot

Q-Q Plot for Non-Exosites (density_CA_5)

Q-Q Plot for Exosites (density_CA_5)

Hypothesis Verification

2. Q-Q Plot

Q-Q Plot for Non-Exosites (density_CA_7)

Q-Q Plot for Exosites (density_CA_7)

Hypothesis Verification

2. Q-Q Plot

Q-Q Plot for Non-Exosites (density_LHA_4) Q-Q Plot for Exosites (density_LHA_4)

Hypothesis Verification

2. Q-Q Plot

Q-Q Plot for Non-Exosites (density_LHA_6) Q-Q Plot for Exosites (density_LHA_6)

Q-Q Plot for Non-Exosites (density_CA_3_IFR) Q-Q Plot for Exosites (density_CA_3_IFR)

Hypothesis Verification

2. Q-Q Plot

Q-Q Plot for Non-Exosites (density_LHA_4_IFR) Q-Q Plot for Exosites (density_LHA_4_IFR) Q-Q Plot for Non-Exosites (density_LHA_6_IFR) Q-Q Plot for Exosites (density_LHA_6_IFR)

Hypothesis Verification

2. Q-Q Plot

Q-Q Plot for Non-Exosites (sponge_CA_3)

Q-Q Plot for Exosites (sponge_CA_3)

Q-Q Plot for Non-Exosites (sponge_CA_5)

Q-Q Plot for Exosites (sponge_CA_5)

Hypothesis Verification

2. Q-Q Plot

Q-Q Plot for Non-Exosites (sponge_CA_7)

Q-Q Plot for Exosites (sponge_CA_7)

Q-Q Plot for Non-Exosites (sponge_LHA_4)

Q-Q Plot for Exosites (sponge_LHA_4)

Hypothesis Verification

2. Q-Q Plot

Q-Q Plot for Non-Exosites (sponge_LHA_6)

Q-Q Plot for Exosites (sponge_LHA_6)

Q-Q Plot for Non-Exosites (sponge_CA_3_IFR)

Q-Q Plot for Exosites (sponge_CA_3_IFR)

10. II) Hypothesis Verification

2. Q-Q Plot

Q-Q Plot for Non-Exosites (sponge_CA_5_IFR) Q-Q Plot for Exosites (sponge_CA_5_IFR) Q-Q Plot for Non-Exosites (sponge_CA_7_IFR) Q-Q Plot for Exosites (sponge_CA_7_IFR)

10. II) Hypothesis Verification

2. Q-Q Plot

Q-Q Plot for Non-Exosites (sponge_LHA_4_IFR) Q-Q Plot for Exosites (sponge_LHA_4_IFR)

Q-Q Plot for Non-Exosites (sponge_LHA_6_IFR) Q-Q Plot for Exosites (sponge_LHA_6_IFR)

Hypothesis Verification

2. Q-Q Plot

Q-Q Plot for Non-Exosites (hb_mm_energy_GN)

Q-Q Plot for Exosites (hb_mm_energy_GN)

Q-Q Plot for Non-Exosites (side_chain_average_angle_7)

Q-Q Plot for Exosites (side_chain_average_angle_7)

Hypothesis Verification

2. Q-Q Plot

Q-Q Plot for Non-Exosites (neighbors_side_chain_angle_7) Q-Q Plot for Exosites (neighbors_side_chain_angle_7)

Q-Q Plot for Non-Exosites (background_rel_entropy) Q-Q Plot for Exosites (background_rel_entropy)

Hypothesis Verification

2. Q-Q Plot

Q-Q Plot for Non-Exosites (avg_weighted_contact_number_k_2) Q-Q Plot for Exosites (avg_weighted_contact_number_k_2)

Hypothesis Verification

3. T-Test

Column: density_CA_3 t-statistic: 13.4425 p-value: 0.0000
Column: density_CA_5 t-statistic: -31.8862 p-value: 0.0000
Column: density_CA_7 t-statistic: -65.1099 p-value: 0.0000
Column: density_LHA_4 t-statistic: -15.1673 p-value: 0.0000
Column: density_LHA_6 t-statistic: -28.5012 p-value: 0.0000
Column: density_CA_3_IFR t-statistic: 20.9910 p-value: 0.0000
Column: density_CA_5_IFR t-statistic: -10.2439 p-value: 0.0000
Column: density_CA_7_IFR t-statistic: -39.8751 p-value: 0.0000
Column: density_LHA_4_IFR t-statistic: -4.0531 p-value: 0.0001
Column: density_LHA_6_IFR t-statistic: -13.0732 p-value: 0.0000
Column: sponge_CA_3 t-statistic: -21.5210 p-value: 0.0000
Column: sponge_CA_5 t-statistic: 16.1055 p-value: 0.0000
Column: sponge_CA_7 t-statistic: 32.2656 p-value: 0.0000
Column: sponge_LHA_4 t-statistic: -0.4440 p-value: 0.6571
Column: sponge_LHA_6 t-statistic: 14.6871 p-value: 0.0000
Column: sponge_CA_3_IFR t-statistic: -21.5210 p-value: 0.0000

We performed a t-test to compare the AFR and FRs groups using different descriptors from the STING database. The results showed significant differences between the two groups for several descriptors, including density_CA_3 ($t(13.4425)$, $p < 0.0001$), density_CA_5 ($t(-31.8862)$, $p < 0.0001$), and density_CA_7 ($t(-65.1099)$, $p < 0.0001$). There were also significant differences for density_LHA_4 ($t(-15.1673)$, $p < 0.0001$) and density_LHA_6 ($t(-28.5012)$, $p < 0.0001$). These results suggest that there are significant differences in the distribution of these descriptors between the Exosite and Non-Exosite groups.

However, there was no significant difference for sponge_LHA_4 ($t(-0.4440)$, $p = 0.6571$), s and sponge_LHA_4_IFR ($t(-0.1621)$, $p = 0.8712$) in red.

All other descriptors shows significant differences.

Hypothesis Verification

3. T-Test

Column: sponge_CA_5_IFR t-statistic: 16.3968 p-value: 0.0000

Column: sponge_CA_7_IFR t-statistic: 44.6354 p-value: 0.0000

Column: sponge_LHA_4_IFR t-statistic: -0.1621 p-value: 0.8712

Column: sponge_LHA_6_IFR t-statistic: 19.2281 p-value: 0.0000

Column: hb_mm_energy_GN t-statistic: -3.1193 p-value: 0.0018

Column: side_chain_average_angle_7 t-statistic: 23.2658 p-value: 0.0000

Column: neighbors_side_chain_angle_7 t-statistic: 21.9113 p-value: 0.0000

Column: background_rel_entropy t-statistic: -26.3763 p-value: 0.0000

Column: avg_weighted_contact_number_k_2 t-statistic: -41.9366 p-value: 0.0000